

Unbundling hackathon orchestration mechanisms:

Relational brokering, contextual configuring, and legitimacy building

Funding: This work was supported by Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, 956745.

SUMMARY

This study explores the orchestration of hackathons targeting the creation of new ideas and innovation. We employed a qualitative case study approach with data collected from hackathon organizers, partners, and solvers at multiple events organized by Ultrahack, a Finnish hackathon organizer. We initially conceptualized hackathon orchestration as a form of coordination that requires brokering in social networks. Building on this background, we empirically identify three types of orchestration mechanisms: orchestration as relational brokering, orchestration as contextual configuring, and orchestration as legitimacy building. We analyze how these mechanisms contribute to the benefits perceived by hackathon solvers and partners. Our study contributes to the academic discourse on orchestration mechanisms in hackathons and offers insights for practitioners managing hackathons and innovation contests, especially from the point of view of third-party orchestrators.

KEYWORDS

orchestration, inter-organizational collaboration, innovation contests, networks, legitimacy, mechanisms, social networks, value creation

1. INTRODUCTION

Hackathons are ideation and innovation contests that rely on the collective efforts of diverse stakeholders and typically last for a predetermined period (Heller et al., 2023; Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021; Rys, 2023). Prior research on hackathons has treated them as innovation competitions and contests (Pihlajamaa & Merisalo, 2021; Cavallo & Burgers, 2024), platforms for learning (Lara & Lockwood, 2016), forms of crowdsourcing and user innovation (Beretta et al., 2022; Browder et al., 2024), temporary gatherings (Kamariotou & Kitsios, 2022), and transdigital spaces (Endrissat & Islam, 2022). Managing and coordinating hackathons is complex (Beretta et al., 2022) and requires collaboration, communication, and transparency (Kathan et al., 2015; Flores et al., 2018).

Hackathons involve multiple stakeholders, including sponsors or partners who provide the problems and challenges and solvers who address those challenges. This presents a highly complex context for orchestrating different views, aspirations, and goals (for a review, see Adamczyk et al., 2012; Heller et al., 2023). The core outcomes of hackathons rely on the often voluntary participation of solvers and their ideation. Prior studies have found that formal coordination works poorly in such contexts (Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021). Hackathons require coordination styles that facilitate affect, engagement, and voluntary action toward collaborative ideation and innovation (Endrissat & Islam, 2022). However, it has recently been pointed out that the existing literature remains ambiguous about the coordination mechanisms that help achieve the creativity and innovation goals of hackathons (Beretta et al., 2022; Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021) and that hackathons remain “a relatively undiscovered and unexplained method” of developing new ideas and inventions (Rys, 2023, p. 501).

We employ the concept and metaphor of *orchestration* (for review, see Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018) to address the research gaps noted above and draw on the insight that hierarchical forms of coordination do not work well in hackathons. Orchestration is a particular form of coordination that aims to enable, facilitate, and empower. It is thus suitable for loosely coupled contexts in which actors are both independent and interdependent (Dharanaj & Parkhe, 2006; Ritala et al., 2023). We believe the orchestration approach is particularly suitable for hackathons, which we view as both social networks (Endrissat & Islam, 2022; Halevy et al., 2019; Kathan et al., 2015; Lara & Lockwood, 2016) and loosely coupled systems (Orton & Weick, 1990). Furthermore, we recognize that hackathon orchestrators should consider the interests and goals of multiple stakeholders while monitoring the overall goals and structure of the hackathon event (Ikävalko & Lempiälä, 2018). In other words, the orchestration of hackathons must accommodate the goals of those hackathon partners who contribute their problems and themes, as well as the solvers who contribute effort and solutions (Heller et al., 2023). Hence, this study asks: *What are the key hackathon orchestration mechanisms, and how do they contribute to partner and solver benefits?*

We partnered with one of the leading and largest organizers of hackathons in Europe, Ultrahack, to investigate hackathon orchestration mechanisms. One of the authors spent three months observing and working alongside Ultrahack staff specializing in hackathon organizing. This allowed us to build our insights via observation and gave us rich access to conduct interviews with organizers, partners, and solvers. We collected interview and observation data on five hackathon events organized by Ultrahack to uncover orchestration mechanisms and how the parties to hackathons perceive them.

We examined hackathon orchestration mechanisms using an abductive research design drawing on brokerage and brokering literature (Halevy et al., 2019; Ritala et al., 2023). We identify three types of orchestration mechanisms: orchestration as relational brokering, orchestration as contextual configuring, and orchestration as legitimacy building. We then demonstrate how those mechanisms contribute to the benefits perceived by hackathon solvers and partners. We contribute to the hackathon literature by demonstrating the important role of *third-party orchestrators* (Pinnington et al., 2021) in facilitating relational connections, configuring an enabling context, attracting resources for the event, and conferring legitimacy. The results complement the existing hackathon literature that has often focused on organization-driven hackathons and their coordination mechanisms (e.g., Bullinger et al., 2010; Heller et al., 2023).

2. CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Using hackathons in a coordinated effort to stimulate ideation and innovation

The idea of innovation contests and the phenomenon of organizing hackathons emerged in the early 1990s (Attalah et al., 2023). While there are no industry statistics, hundreds of companies around the world have organized innovation contests and staged thousands of hackathons for other organizations (Adameczyk et al., 2012; Heller et al., 2023). While hackathons originally gained popularity in information technology contexts (Lara & Lockwood, 2016; Rys, 2023), they are now employed by both private sector innovators and governmental organizations such as NASA, the European Union, and the World Bank, which have used hackathons to expand their innovation capabilities and find solutions to challenges.

Hackathons are intensive two- or three-day innovation events where new solutions, products, and/or services are conceptualized and developed (Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021). They have been

described as “idea competitions on specific topics in the form of a time-limited event” (Attalah et al., 2023, p. 2) or competitive events where “participants work in small teams over a short period of time to ideate, design, rapidly prototype and test their ideas with a user-centric approach to solve a determined challenge” (Tucci et al., 2019, p. 1). Hackathons bring together a diverse group of solvers, both expert and non-expert, to conceptualize, prototype, and develop new products and services in a short space of time (Lodato & DiSalvo, 2016).

Hackathons have also been described as “accelerated innovation processes that bring together individuals to voluntarily develop new products to solve specific and ambitious challenges in an extremely limited and ad hoc time frame” (Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021, p. 684). They represent distinct forms of organizing and participation that fall outside the classic intra-organizational ideation and innovation processes. In this regard, hackathons collate many of the ideas of open innovation by exchanging reciprocal knowledge and creating synergies via knowledge flows and knowledge creation (West & Bogers, 2014). The most common setting is that of an established organization searching for external ideas (see, e.g., Browder et al., 2023; Cavallo & Burgers, 2024), corresponding to inbound open innovation. Furthermore, the initiator (i.e., the sponsor) of a hackathon often strategically shares information and makes use of the benefits of outbound open innovation (Attalah et al., 2023) while continuing to benefit from inbound knowledge flows coming from hackathon solvers.

While hackathons appear to work well with relatively light coordination (Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021), they are not easy to organize effectively. However, Heller et al. (2023) identified the basic building blocks of hackathon organizing for the pre-, mid-, and post-event phases, and there are a variety of design elements used across different hackathons (Bullinger et al., 2010). Essentially, the orchestrator of the hackathon has a major role in designing mechanisms to

engage, involve, and incentivize actors in different roles because the motivation of solvers, sponsors, and the organizer is likely to vary (e.g., Garcia, 2022; Heller et al., 2023; Pe-Than et al., 2022).

The present study has a particular interest in hackathons not only as a form of open innovation but also as social networks where solvers share and create knowledge. The social network approach illustrates how hackathon participants interact and create knowledge and how hackathon orchestrators, as third-party actors, can intervene in those social structures to facilitate interaction and creativity (Halevy et al., 2019). The literature highlights the role of the network orchestrator in such networks (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018; Ritala et al., 2023). In the next section, we discuss hackathons from the point of view of orchestrated social networks.

2.2. Orchestration of hackathons: social network and brokering view

Scholars originally used the orchestration concept to describe the coordination of a networked context where actors are loosely coupled (Dhanaraj & Parkhe, 2006; Ritala et al., 2009), which means that they are independent in terms of what they do but interdependent in creating value together. Later research adopted the orchestration term as a broad metaphor to explain various approaches to network orchestration across multiple levels of analysis, ranging from innovation network orchestration to facilitation of social settings and communities (see Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018). In this section, we first briefly review the orchestration literature and then discuss our own theoretical approach to orchestration as a process of brokering that takes place in social networks (e.g., Halevy et al., 2019; Ritala et al., 2023).

Initially, the concept of orchestration integrated alliance and network theory and was defined as a “set of deliberate, purposeful actions undertaken by the hub firm as it seeks to create value (expand the pie) and extract value (gain a larger slice of the pie) from the network” (Dhanaraj & Parkhe, 2006). Relatedly, it has been seen as an organization’s “capability to purposefully build and manage inter-firm innovation networks” where individual- and organizational-level orchestration capabilities interact (Ritala et al., 2009:571). In this initial period, and also more recently, orchestration has been used to refer to a style of network coordination that focuses on facilitation, visioning, and enabling and that often takes place in innovative and entrepreneurial network settings (e.g., Faccin et al., 2020; Tabas et al., 2023). Over time, these network perspectives on orchestration were also adopted in the literature on business, innovation, and platform ecosystems. In this regard, Autio (2022:12) refers to orchestration as a “set of deliberate and purposeful actions undertaken by the ecosystem orchestrator to encourage voluntary, value co-creating inputs and effect coordination among hierarchically independent ecosystem of the ecosystem.”

Another central discussion in the network orchestration literature focuses on how orchestration aligns with the goals of the focal entity as opposed to those of the other network actors. As discussed above, orchestration may broadly follow the goals defined by the orchestrator that it pursues to acquire support from other actors (e.g., Dhanaraj & Parkhe, 2006). Some orchestrator types involve individual or even opportunistic goals, an example being “player-orchestrators” with a competitive orientation (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018). However, the literature acknowledges that orchestration outcomes cannot be managed but merely deliberately influenced by the orchestrator, and some research recognizes that orchestration can also involve more open-ended and alter-oriented approaches (Giudici et al., 2018; Ritala et al., 2023). In this regard, “facilitator-orchestrators” focus on collective goals

and common interests and use their relational power to achieve them (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018). Similarly, an “alter-oriented orchestrator” focuses on the alters’ benefits and aims to influence others to help them achieve their goals rather than focusing on the orchestrator’s benefits (Ritala et al., 2023).

Orchestration occurs when an orchestrator performs a particular role. These roles refer to what orchestrators do and include bundles of activities and capabilities that are decisive for the outcomes of the orchestration (Ritala et al., 2009; Tabas et al., 2023). Bundles of orchestration capabilities are shaped by the context, and their social environment “affects the perceived roles, orchestration activities needed, and identity of actors” (Tabas et al., 2023: 226). Orchestrator capabilities bridge orchestrator types and roles, that is, how orchestrators adopt roles and how successfully they perform those roles. Accordingly, roles are implemented according to orchestrator type, and they may be switched or additional ones adopted if the orchestrator detects network or environmental changes that call for an adaptation of orchestration (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018). Importantly, orchestration literature has also identified further roles and activities that are useful in encouraging creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurial activity. A “business facilitator” spotting new opportunities or a “regulation informant” offering training must be able to facilitate support and exchange expertise (see Tabas et al., 2023). Furthermore, relationship promotion is an essential capability for orchestrating collaboration (Goduscheit, 2014; Tabas et al., 2023). Orchestrators may also specialize in building or extending technology-focused or market-focused relationships, acting as “knowledge brokers” who promote relationships with actors who are not members of an organization (Goduscheit, 2014:526). In addition to “relationship promoters”, facilitating collaboration involves roles that negotiate and promote fairness and transparency, “coordinators” who are able to communicate collaboration benefits, and “commanders” who

mobilize, promote benefits and trust, and guide network development and production activities to create prerequisites for successful orchestration (see Tabas et al., 2023:227-232). Finally, “facilitator-orchestrators” aim to intermediate and foster innovation, as well as collaboration. They must employ integrity and neutrality in the role (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018:4). This seems highly appropriate in hackathon settings, which tend to keep formal rules to a minimum and focus on flexibility and adaptation.

Given the variety of perspectives in the orchestration literature across different levels of analysis and theoretical backgrounds, this study adopts a social network view of orchestration in which the orchestrator acts as a broker embedded in a social network setting (Ritala et al., 2023). This approach serves us particularly well given our empirical context of third-party orchestration (see also Pinnington et al., 2021), in which the hackathons are orchestrated by a separate entity wishing to align and enable activity and knowledge exchange in networked settings. Accordingly, we examine orchestration as a process of brokering in social networks (Halevy et al., 2019; Ritala et al., 2023). From the brokering perspective, the orchestrating entity (whether an individual or an organization) intermediates and coordinates other actors in the social network to interact with one another (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018). We follow the definition offered by Ritala et al. (2023) suggesting network orchestration is a “set of activities and roles performed by a hub actor (individual, team, or organization) to coordinate independent network members’ interactions within a loosely coupled context.”

The brokering activities conducted by the orchestrating entity have most often been viewed as *intermediation* (Halevy et al., 2019), in which actor A helps actors B and C to connect and interact; a phenomenon also known as bridging a structural hole (Burt, 2004). Brokering is a well-known phenomenon in a variety of settings, including intra-organizational settings where

brokering helps to bridge connections and knowledge between different groups (Johnson et al., 2023), as well as broader community settings where brokering often takes place via boundary-spanning roles (Bullinger et al., 2010). Beyond such intermediation and bridging roles, Halevy and colleagues (2019) noted that the brokering by actor A can also *modify* the interaction between actors B and C. In these cases, B and C might already be connected, but A would intervene and change the interaction by providing additional resources or inputs that contribute to and thus modify that interaction context. Both of these brokering mechanisms are likely to feature in hackathon orchestration, given the central role of the orchestrator not only in bringing actors together but also in designing how the interaction, ideation, and overall activities play out during the event.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Empirical context and data collection

We employed a qualitative case study method (Yin, 2014) focusing on one empirical context to which we had exclusive access for a prolonged period. The aim of this approach is to reach a level of thick description that provides context-dependent insights (Geertz, 1973; Guba & Lincoln, 1994). We can then derive inferences that help answer the research question. Our empirical context involves hackathons organized by Ultrahack, a hackathon organizer based in Finland. Typically, a hackathon organized by Ultrahack is a “collaboration and co-creation process, including intense development sprint (usually 48h)” where teams with different competencies and backgrounds address real-life challenges formulated by companies or public organizations (Ultrahack, 2021). Ultrahack’s concept includes inviting teams to bring fresh ideas and to encourage out-of-the-box and even radically innovative thinking rather than incremental development. Ultrahack supports teams by providing mentoring by experts from

different fields. The teams pitch their solutions at the end of the event, with the best teams being awarded a prize. The evaluation criteria used by the organizer typically include five main elements: innovativeness, user benefits, team or individual talent, technical solution aspects, and challenge fit.

This study relies on qualitative data collected by the first author during a three-month field visit at Ultrahack lasting from September to December 2022. The study thus benefits from data on hackathon organization and execution drawn from all involved parties (organizers, partners, and solvers). This research focuses on three onsite hackathons and two hybrid events, in which part of the hackathon setting was onsite and another part online. Onsite settings enable more direct observation of and interaction with the actors involved. All the observed events were software- and technology-focused (see Heller et al., 2023) and aimed to develop ideas and solutions to the problems advanced by the hackathon partners.

The analysis is based on qualitative individual and group interviews ($n = 23$), informal conversations with the actors involved, field notes, and observations made during active participation (see Table I).

TABLE I Overview of hackathon events and empirical data.

Data source	Amount of data	Interview duration	Role in the analysis	Purpose of the interviews
Orchestrator interviews	11 interviews with 5 different organizers of the hackathons	1. 51 min 2. 54 min 3. 25 min 4. 70 min 5. 35 min 6. 27 min 7. 47 min 8. 91 min 9. 40 min 10. 53 min 11. 26 min	Inductive analysis of orchestration mechanisms	To gather insights into the orchestrators' view on organizing, facilitating, and orchestrating their hackathon events.
Partner interviews	8 interviews with 8 different partners	1. 47 min 2. 40 min 3. 52 min 4. 22 min 5. 16 min 6. 52 min 7. 64 min 8. 16 min	Analysis of partner benefits	To gather insights into the partners' view on how the hackathon events were organized, facilitated, and orchestrated.
Solvers interviews	4 group interviews with: 1) Team of 3 solvers 2) Team of 2 solvers 3) Team of 2 solvers 4) Team of 2 solvers 1 informal interview / audio note, individual solver	1. 47 min 2. 53 min 3. 65 min 4. 78 min	Analysis of solver benefits	To gather insights into solvers' views on how the hackathon events were organized, facilitated, and orchestrated.
Field notes	Field notes from 5 hackathons (3 audio notes, 23 pages of written notes)		Triangulation, Onsite observation	To gather insights into orchestrator's views on how this hackathon research corresponds to their organizing, facilitating, and orchestrating activities.

3.2 Data analysis

The study was conducted using abductive analysis of qualitative data, field notes, and observations that provide an understanding of the organizing process and the related orchestration. The unit of analysis is a hackathon event. The data analysis focused on capturing the different micro-level orchestration activities. First, open coding was used, and all the instances from the data that pointed to orchestration activities were inductively coded. In the second stage, we structured first-order codes into emerging themes focused on the orchestrator's activities. Third, abductive reasoning between brokering theory and empirics elicited three core theoretical themes that we call relational brokering, contextual configuring, and legitimacy building. Fourth, we triangulated evidence on the benefits of the three orchestration mechanisms based on the interview data, field notes, and observations. Finally, we triangulated these understandings with representatives from Ultrahack, who confirmed that our interpretation was a reasonable reflection of the events, pointing to a sufficient level of face validity. Their confirmation supported our findings and ensured we had not misunderstood issues relating to their organizing of hackathons.

Below, we refer to those individuals and teams engaged in addressing the challenge(s) at a hackathon event as *solvers* to differentiate them from other participants. However, we note that the interviewees often refer to solvers as *participants* in the interview material. Organizations collaborating with the organizer are referred to as *partners*; again, in some interviews, partners are referred to as clients. Finally, the hackathon organizer team facilitating and leading the event is referred to as the *orchestrator*.

4. FINDINGS

We investigate the key hackathon orchestration mechanisms and how they contribute to partner and solver benefits. We identified three orchestration mechanisms specific to hackathons—relational brokering, contextual configuring, and legitimacy building—that serve distinct purposes and accommodate different target outcomes and benefits. The organizers’ time is mainly spent on brokering, but significant effort is also expended on contextual configuring and legitimacy building. While all three mechanisms are novel in hackathon research, our findings align with brokering literature, which has discussed relational brokering and contextual configuring in the context of knowledge networks (Ritala et al., 2023). Legitimacy building is a well-established concept in institutional theory and is widely discussed in various contexts, including networks and ecosystems. However, it has not been previously highlighted as a brokering mechanism for fast-paced events such as hackathons, as a process that needs to be continuously created, recreated, and conquered (Suddaby et al., 2017).

4.1 Orchestration as relational brokering

Orchestrators mobilize actors at a hackathon to interact and create value. Given this intent, we view orchestration as constituting brokering activities, particularly pro-social behaviors of orchestrators that can influence a social network by accommodating partners’ needs and aspirations (Ritala et al., 2023). Brokers (here: hackathon orchestrators) are individuals who build and form relationships with other individuals in a social network.

Brokering in hackathons has multiple layers. Hackathons start with a partner that sets the problem for the event, so the first layer of brokering starts before the event and continues after it concludes, aiming to build the set-up for the hackathon (collaboration brokering and facilitation). Second, the broker must ensure that the actors’ interests (especially partners and

solvers) align. The third and fourth elements of brokering operate at a more practical level to ensure that effective solver teams are formed and that the interaction works across different hackathon settings (online, hybrid, or onsite). At the end of the section, we highlight the benefits of brokering activities for partners and solvers.

FIGURE 1

Orchestration as relational brokering: Data structure.

Collaboration brokering and facilitation is established by the orchestrator, who acts as a broker between partners and solvers and enables social network-building before, during, and after the event. Collaboration brokerage in hackathons happens when the orchestrator facilitates interactions between various actors and actor groups, such as the private and public sectors and different industries. Facilitation for this collaboration is important because it enables sharing industry expertise. In addition, the orchestrator facilitates communication with and among solvers. Brokering activities before a hackathon event takes place can include introductory webinars and mentoring sessions, and, during the event, interaction facilitation through

community meetups. After an event, brokering may continue and include the continuation of projects:

We're almost like a broker in between, where we match our customers' objectives with participants and their objectives. We offer them a platform to connect and a process through which they can build a collaboration. ...We offer them a structure and a model that we feel [can make] both successful. (Organizer 2)

Another important aspect is *aligning interests* between actors. The orchestrator needs to understand what each key partner wants from the hackathon event:

The partners have different roles. Some have a strong brand and can provide mentoring and marketing support, but they don't bring any financial support. Others don't have that much marketing support [to give], but they can support financially. So, we need to [bring] that together to create a feasible package. (Organizer 1)

The orchestrator balances the interests of the various partners to ensure the event appeals to the target audience. As Organizer 1 put it: "It's also balancing how to make it interesting for the right audience." The process produces common goals for the hackathon event and supports collaboration. Of course, full alignment between partner goals is rarely possible, but the multi-partner hackathon objectives are a balanced compromise. Nevertheless, it is important to achieve sufficient alignment to ensure the event proceeds unhindered by confusing or conflicting goals.

Third, a highly practical aspect of brokering relates to the *selection and matchmaking* of teams participating in a hackathon: "[As to] team selection, usually we do [it] one, two, three days

after the registration deadline, depending on the objective of the client” (Organizer 5). Matchmaking can be considered a success if the parties have different skill sets but similar backgrounds: “Single registrants...you guys have similar backgrounds in terms of education and skills, but also location. People are rather sensitive to the location and cultural aspects” (Organizer 5). As the individual registrants do not know one another, trust must be built first. Rather than forced matchmaking, the organizer offers options: “They decide, but we sort of say, ‘Here are your options.’ This skill set might match this skill set. It’s like speed dating” (Organizer 4). To encourage newly formed teams of strangers to communicate with one another, the orchestrator typically uses icebreaking activities to initiate conversations.

Finally, another practical aspect of brokering is the *interaction between different participation formats*: onsite, hybrid, and online settings. While online hackathons may require less effort by the orchestrator and are easier for solvers to participate in than onsite formats, there is a downside in terms of networking opportunities, getting to know people, and experiencing the atmosphere. Many solvers participate in hackathons because of the networking opportunities, meeting new people, and generally experiencing the event. In an onsite setting, teams are in the same location, so knowledge sharing and exchanging ideas with other teams and mentors occur more naturally: “Onsite...was much more impactful. ...So, I liked that format. That was more fun for me” (Partner 7). The best experience comes from onsite events because they allow for personal interactions. As Organizer 4 put it, solvers are “interested in each other’s projects. ...People like to talk to each other, and they like to meet each other, and that’s one of the things that we frequently hear in feedback, which is one of the coolest parts.”

Essentially, the orchestrator’s brokering behaviors benefit solvers by offering them opportunities to add peers, mentors, industry experts, and potential employers to their

networks. Getting in front of companies and the industry can bring job and career opportunities for solvers and the potential connections available will often influence which hackathons they participate in: “It depends on how the hackathon is managed. You have to take that into consideration [as a solver]: what you want from the hackathon” (Team 3, Solver 7). Solvers also benefit from matchmaking targeted at team formation. Bringing together individuals from different backgrounds builds on the idea of creative problem solving but can also foster experiences with diverse teams: “The most frustrating thing ever is when you implement something technically ambitious, and then you lose to someone who has a beautiful slideshow...but no technical implementation” (Team 1, Solver 1). Being matched with unfamiliar people can lead to new network ties forged during a hackathon: “Matchmaking is nice because you might meet a talented person that you would be able to work with. You never know. It might [provide] more networking opportunities” (Team 2, Solver 5). On occasion, new connections may also lead to mentorships and even friendships.

For their part, hackathon partners benefit from meeting solvers, attracting top talent, and building strategic partnerships with other organizations that facilitate the sharing of knowledge and ideas, potentially leading to learning and innovation. This requires the different actors to commit to building trust: “One thing that affected the level of trust was that every partner who organized the hackathon was very committed to making it happen” (Partner 7). Learning and innovation benefits occur when the solvers’ suggestions offer partners ideas to resolve their challenges. Orchestration mechanisms assist in knowledge exchanges and encourage participation from various stakeholders, leading them to create their own communities of innovation.

4.2 Orchestration as Contextual Configuring

Orchestration means not only brokering people and organizational relationships through intermediation but also configuring the structures, settings, and roles of the participating actors (Halevy et al., 2019). Importantly, configuring the relational context can involve the role of brokers as mediators in contexts involving conflict and resolution between different groups, leading to positively shifting value perceptions via a process labeled *bridgework* (Johnson et al., 2023). We found contextual configuring took place via three distinct activities: adaptations of format, responding to feedback, and clarity in roles, rules, and criteria. Together, these activities lead to consistent and improving structures, as well as clarity of roles, rules, and expectations, providing a reliable setting for hackathon orchestration.

FIGURE 2

Orchestration as contextual configuring: Data structure.

Hackathons are fast-paced events and typically involve considerable *ad hoc adaptation* and sudden changes in the event program to configure the hackathon context to meet the needs arising as it proceeds. Examples of such changes include altering visuals and last-minute

communications. Such changes are extremely difficult to anticipate but can influence whether a hackathon is successful. For instance, in partner companies' management, leaders may change, or project responsibilities may be transferred to other managers. This can lead to sudden changes on the partners' side, which may prompt them to ask the organizers for ad hoc changes. Such changes often refer to communication issues, such as visual communication. "Big updates...(happen, for example, when) people change their minds. Management changes, so they (partners) must adapt to their new management. That happens all the time. ... It is usually to do with communication like, oh, they don't like the visual anymore. That's a very common one." (Organizer 5). The orchestrator tries to clarify the partner's needs well ahead of the event, to be able to present a clear schedule. Requests for ad hoc changes might come in too late to be integrated into that schedule. "Sometimes a bit last minute. (Such as) Oh, we wanted to review the participants' code to make sure it's current. Yeah, we (the organizers) have one hour for evaluation; we don't have time to sit behind the computer for half an hour for each team. It's not possible anymore in the schedule" (Organizer 5).

Another form of contextual adaptation is based on *continuous feedback* from previously arranged, similar events, allowing the improvement of hackathon designs based on solver and partner feedback and partner-specific key performance indicators, particularly when dealing with repeated iterations of hackathons with the same partner. The organizer designs the format in collaboration with the partners, according to their needs and their feasibility. Discussion with the partners enables the organizer to clarify the design of the hackathon format and identify suitable solver groups. The format is adapted also to match the solvers' expectations based on their feedback. Consistent feedback mechanisms help the organizer understand partner preferences and the most important aspects for them, for example, recruiting candidates, networking with other industry leaders, or getting feedback and input on their newly developed

technology: “[We are] going through those KPIs, what they (client and partners) expect to happen after” (Organizer 1). Repeated iterations of hackathons provide the chance to gather feedback that leads to organizational learning. The organizers can prove their expertise and demonstrate well-established processes and consulting skills to their partners during this process. “In the beginning, first year (preparation time with the client), maybe it was two months, then...three months, and now, for next time, we’ve already discussed that we should start (one year ahead). ...Since it has been done three times, we can demonstrate that this is how it looks, these are our results, everybody has been happy, both partners and participants” (Organizer 1). Multiple iterations and repeated feedback lead to learning for the partners, too: “Third time. We were developing it all the time, and we’re going to continue next year” (Partner 5). Such continuous improvement also influences the partners’ decision to continue the collaboration.

Clarity in roles, rules, and criteria facilitates trust-based work relationships (Curnin et al., 2015); our results show it forms part of the orchestration process in terms of context. Organizer 5 put it as follows: “Designing the schedule and making sure there is room for everything that we plan for the schedule...managing these different stakeholders, suppliers, and providers that are needed for an event to happen.” Orchestrators manage those stakeholders and act as the main point of contact for the key actors. Organizer 5 noted that “as part of the job here, I host the event. I’m the main point of contact. ...I’m that reliable person; I’m the host...making sure everything runs smoothly, but also the face and point of contact between the different stakeholders.” The inclusion of additional partners, such as technology partners, is established in discussions between the organizer and the main client or partner(s). “...there’s a first discussion between the challenge owner so that there are not too many. ...While things are unclear, it’s good to not have too many” (Organizer 1). The orchestrator holds discussions with

partners early to establish clear rules to avoid confusion and problems later. “We write what the KPIs are. So then, (it) cannot be that it’s only beneficial for some of them. It needs to support all of them. One of the skills we’ve learned is to have these difficult discussions very early and agree on things. Then, we don’t have to have these uncomfortable discussions later” (Organizer 1). Furthermore, hackathon evaluation criteria and rules are usually announced ahead of the event, and solvers look at them for guidance. When criteria and resources are announced beforehand, equal access to mentoring, coaching, and learning supports reliability and helps establish credibility: “In the previous...hackathon, I remember when brainstorming with the team, like...a few days before, we were looking at the rules and saying, okay, so we can only look at what data we can download, whether there is a library that can do that because open source was allowed” (Individual Solver 1). Exploiting the organizer’s knowledge and experience and combining it with the partners’ and solvers’ needs means credible roles, rules, and a clear process are established in a reliable and trustworthy context.

Successful contextual configuration ensures that solvers have the necessary resources, tools, and datasets to develop their solutions effectively while also building a creative atmosphere that participants enjoy. Solvers are often passionate about exploring new technologies: “The coolest hackathons are usually ones where you get to explore some new technology or some completely new solution domain” (Team 1, Solver 1). Solvers see hackathons as catalysts for new ideas and opportunities to extend their networks and socialize. They also appreciate the diversity of solvers, having fun, laughing, being on a good team, experiencing a positive atmosphere, and learning. Teaming up with other creative individuals in a stimulating environment that spurs ideation is motivating, as that is not often found in their normal work lives. A structured environment with well-organized schedules and clear objectives helps solvers to manage their time and efforts.

For partners, effective contextual configuration ensures that the solutions developed are relevant, valuable, and aligned with the goals set for the event. Structure brings clarity and fosters efficient use of resources, while criteria and guidelines ensure that solutions meet the standards for quality and relevance. Ad hoc adaptations facilitate a seamless event experience, minimizing disruptions and ensuring that key performance indicators are met.

For both solvers and partners, the most important benefit stemming from contextual configuration is the creation of an event that assures knowledge sharing, learning, and the development of new ideas. For example, “they were able to evolve the idea. ... How this technology could be deployed in a tram, and then there was [company] and [company] people brainstorming that idea further. So, it was very fruitful” (Partner 7). Solvers perceived the benefits of competing: “It’s cool to compete with some of the teams when you realize they have the same abilities. So, it’s interesting to compete, and it also pushes you to work harder and come up with better ideas” (Team 3, Solver 6). Similarly, solvers enjoyed the learning experience—“I had never used (the program), and here I got ...to make some stuff that for a beginner I was proud of. So, I think it’s cool, and I walk away from here now knowing this” (Team 1, Solver 3)—and especially learning from others’ solutions: “I liked seeing others’ solutions because ours failed, so it was nice to see what others did in the [allotted] time” (Team 2, Solver 4).

These support members of diverse groups in building positive relationships among themselves and with organizations by positively impacting identity formation, which, in turn, supports bottom-up processes geared toward inclusivity. Brokering relationships involves thus “addressing conscious or subconscious perceptions of value and worthiness” to effect change

in the right direction. As bridgework for inclusion is seen as a mutual process, “traditional top-down formal policies and procedures” additionally need “individuals who are a part of the everyday social fabric of work life are integral for making substantive changes related to creating inclusive climates in the workplace” (Johnson et al., 2023:1480).

4.3 Orchestration as legitimacy building

Legitimacy encompasses the appropriateness of actions within a socially constructed system of norms (Suchman, 1995). Building legitimacy, or legitimating, is an interactive process in which a change agent makes a purposive effort to negotiate, construct, and maintain legitimacy (Suddaby et al., 2017). In the practice of orchestrating hackathons, this relates to orchestrator-focused legitimation, building a network of partners and supporters, framing hackathons, building momentum, and deliberate use of space. In essence, the orchestrator confronts a multifaceted challenge: one needs to legitimate not only the orchestration actions but also the hackathon event itself, its arrangements, and the partner organizations’ objectives for the hackathon. We view the two processes as complementary: as the orchestrating entity gains legitimacy, it can signal legitimacy for individual hackathons also, and vice versa over time, as a positively perceived hackathon legitimates the orchestrating entity.

FIGURE 3

Orchestration as legitimacy building: Data structure.

Building *orchestrator-focused legitimation* is key to having solvers and partners follow orchestrating actions without a formal hierarchy, and building trust and long-term relationships is a key aspect in this regard. For the orchestrator to establish trust with partners, a strong relationship is needed: the orchestrator “is seen as a good partner to run hackathons with. ...It’s simply trust in their abilities to perform. There are [other] clients, there’s a history behind the company” (Partner 6). By clarifying and communicating the benefits, the orchestrator fosters the legitimacy to act: the individual working with partners on behalf of the organizer “does know a lot of people and is able to explain the benefits of using a hackathon to advance business and stuff like that and gain advantages” (Organizer 4).

The legitimacy of the orchestration is linked to and depends on the quality of the *network of affiliated partners and supporters*. Building that network requires time and experience in organizing multiple hackathons, which in turn enables the facilitation of productive interactions between the different actors involved in the hackathon (partners, mentors, and solvers):

“We had a lot of discussions with the mentors. So, not just the teams, and it was fruitful, and ... it was nice to discuss with them. So, it was also information sharing between companies and cities and that kind of thing that made the network there.” (Partner 1)

The solvers should also have diverse skills and backgrounds, requiring broad networks and heterogeneous pools from which they can be recruited. This wide reach allows partners to “have broader connections with the actual operators of the field outside the university” (Partner 3).

Beyond legitimation in the eyes of partners, the hackathon event itself needs to be legitimate in the eyes of the solvers. Hence, the *hackathon challenge and scope* are framed and tailored to each event and should be clearly defined so that solvers and mentors work efficiently toward a shared goal. As one partner put it, “The problem was defined very well on day zero. Everyone participating seemed like we understood the problem that we were attempting to solve in the context that was given” (Partner 6). A clear problem definition allows all the actors to focus readily on solving the problem: “There was no back and forth on how should we do it, what should we do. It was rather, it was a surprisingly clear focus on execution over communication” (Partner 6).

There is also an aspect of *building momentum* through various activities before and during the event. Multiple aspects, from a catchy title and marketing visuals to credible partners, help build the legitimacy of an event:

“I remember I went to view their web pages, and there was a list of hackathons that they had organized before, and there were big brands, such as [company] and other cities, universities, and big companies, so that also increased their credibility for me.” (Partner 7)

A well-orchestrated event leads to solvers assessing their time was well spent: “Even if you lose, it wouldn’t have been a waste of time. You got some knowledge out of it” (Team 3, Solver 7). During the hackathon event, orchestrating an engaging atmosphere for innovation is vital. A good “energy” is attractive for solvers and was described as “infectious” by drawing in solvers and sparking their curiosity: “It was nice to see that it’s proceeding, and also this innovation work around it, it’s very ... vivid maybe, or very active” (Partner 1). Getting professional feedback promoted solvers’ perceptions of being supported: “You know that you’re going to get feedback ... there are going to be people who will be like; you get feedback, you get one-on-one mentoring, you have good support, so that’s good” (Team 3, Solver 7).

Finally, *space and surroundings* can increase the prominence of hackathons. Locations are chosen to convey a technology-oriented, futuristic atmosphere. Professional lighting is employed to make a powerful visual impression: “The environment was well set up, and it was kind of, let’s say, futuristic, with lasers going in the ceiling and stuff like that: kind of, start-up buzz stuff” (Partner 8).

For the solvers, these legitimating behaviors provide recognition of their efforts and

achievements. Participation, let alone winning a well-regarded hackathon, adds credibility to their CVs. It also allows them to showcase their work and abilities to a broad audience, including media, potential employers, and industry leaders. Appropriate rewards for participation will motivate solvers because their efforts are recognized. It is seen as a privilege to be among the first to develop something novel, and a professional evaluation of solvers' technological skills is an additional benefit. At the same time, solvers are aware that partner companies also benefit from hackathons: "It's a good deal for the companies to get something out of this" (Team 2, Solver 4). Nevertheless, solvers were skeptical about the use of hackathons as an alternative to R&D development work in organizations. Providing free labor saves costs for organizations, which makes the orchestrator's negotiating and balancing actions even more important.

A legitimate hackathon enhances the reputation of the hackathon partners as innovators and supporters of new talent. This also builds trust and reputation among a broad range of stakeholders. While solvers may seek future employers, the clients clearly benefit from having the opportunity to attract future talent from among the solvers and to find new collaborators among other hackathon partners: "To the customer [it's] the opportunity to recruit new talent. That's very clearly the case, raising their profile as a key player in the community" (Organizer 4). The legitimating efforts of the orchestrator should also attract media attention for the hackathon, which will enhance positive reputations and boost visibility for the firm, industry, and the issue for which the solution is sought. As such, "every client is interested ... in the ultimate solutions being of quality. They are doing it for communication purposes" (Organizer 5). While challenges are not often explicitly set to use specific technology, partners would naturally like to see solutions that use their own technology, thus promoting it to solvers and users. Seeing future applications of their technology demonstrated may also help build

legitimacy for their future products or help decide whether to continue projects with those technologies.

4.4. Synthesis of the results: Three hackathon orchestration mechanisms

Table II summarizes the three identified orchestration mechanisms, how they create value for hackathon organizers and stakeholders, and how different hackathon partners and solvers perceive the benefits of those three mechanisms.

Relational brokering provides access to social networks formed at hackathon events. Solvers can benefit from expanded professional networks and sometimes unexpected new connections. Partners can benefit from relational brokering via connections to potential new talent, aligning the event with their goals, and building partnerships with the broader community around their business or technology challenges.

Contextual configuring helps create favorable environments for learning, experimenting, and other experiences. For solvers, this means creative atmospheres, structured settings, access to relevant resources, and being entertained, all factors that maintain solver engagement in a hackathon. For partners, contextual configuring helps ensure successful knowledge sharing and bolsters the quality and relevance of hackathon outputs.

Finally, legitimacy-building mechanisms attract acceptance, resources, and attention from different stakeholders regarding the hackathon's main theme(s) and technology, and the event itself. Solvers benefit from legitimacy building by being involved in reputable events in which different kinds of recognition, rewards, and publicity reinforce the value they obtain from their

participation. For partners, legitimacy building improves their own brand image, stakeholder trust, talent acquisition, and potential media coverage.

TABLE II Orchestration mechanisms for the creation of value and solver and partner benefits.

Orchestration mechanism	Key value creation logics	Solver benefits	Partner benefits
<i>Relational brokering</i>	Providing access to networks, bringing diverse networks together	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expanding professional networks - Experiencing diversity - Unexpected encounters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connecting with and finding talent - Building new partnerships - Building communities of innovation - Alignment with the goals of the event
<i>Contextual configuring</i>	Creating a favorable environment for learning, experimenting, and experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enjoying and having fun during the event - Creative atmosphere for learning and knowledge development - Structured environment for participation - Access to technology and resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sharing knowledge and ideas - Quality and relevance of the developed solutions
<i>Legitimacy building</i>	Attracting acceptance, resources, and attention to the issue, technology, or solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognition - Credibility - Publicity - Rewards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brand image - Stakeholder trust - Talent acquisition - Media coverage

Furthermore, it is important to note that the three orchestration practices identified were not distributed fully equally across the time span of the hackathon events we analyzed. Similarly, as mentioned in the previous literature (e.g., Heller et al., 2023), also in our empirical context hackathon events included pre-, during- and post-hackathon phases that the orchestrator was responsible for coordinating. Table III provides a timeline of the orchestration mechanisms during the major phases of hackathons and identifies the orchestration activities relevant to each stage.

In the case of our empirical context, we identify the pre-event phase, four different phases during the hackathon event itself, and the post-event phase. The *pre-event phase* takes place

before the hackathon and includes all the hackathon-related preparation, communication, and interaction between the hackathon orchestrator and other relevant parties. The second phase begins when the hackathon has officially started and is named the *start of the event* phase. Subsequent activities revolve around a *solution development phase*, at the end of which participating teams of solvers hand in a solution to the competition. Following the hand-in of their solution, the teams present it in a pitch to an audience, in what is referred to as the *pitching* phase. In the subsequent phase, the previously presented solutions are evaluated by a jury which is referred to as the *evaluation* phase. This phase also includes the presentation of the outcomes of the evaluation, and relatedly, the announcement of the winning solutions and teams, and an award ceremony. Finally, a follow-up phase starts after the event has concluded and is referred to as the *post-event* phase. In the following, using the evidence from the interviews and from our observations, we discuss how the different orchestration mechanisms were distributed temporally across hackathon phases (see also Table III).

Relational brokering. The orchestrator provides various actors participating in the hackathons access to diverse networks through collaboration brokering, which takes place starting from pre-event and during all the actual event phases. Alignment of interests is orchestrated from the pre-event phase onwards until the solution development phase. Team selection and matchmaking take place only at the pre-event and the start of the event phases. Finally, from the pre-event stage onwards and throughout the hackathon event, the interaction between the onsite, hybrid, or online participation formats is configured by the orchestrator.

Contextual configuring. The design of a hackathon event format, while similar in many cases, is adapted to each event. Designing an event is based on continuous feedback from clients, partners, and solvers, this happens in both pre-event and post-event phases. During the event,

the format is adapted in an ad hoc manner. This ad hoc adaptation takes place in the first three phases of the actual event, beginning from the start of the event and ending in the pitching phase. Roles, rules, and criteria need to be clear (and clarified by the orchestrator when necessary) right from the beginning, including, for example, the roles of partners and clients prior and during to the event until the end of the event.

Legitimacy building. Orchestrator legitimation is gained, built, and expanded during all the phases, though less so in the solution development phase. Furthermore, networks of affiliated partners and supporters are generally built or extended throughout a hackathon event; however, the pitching phase focuses uniquely on the solvers' presentations and thus there is not much networking going on during that phase. Hackathon challenge framing and scope adjustment are uniquely done in the pre-event phase. Conversely, momentum is built throughout the pre-event and the event phase as a variety of hackathon participants become more engaged with the event. Finally, during the actual hackathon event, physical space and surroundings are used to increase prominence, while the pre- and post-event parts operate mostly in digital settings and thus spatial aspects do not play a major role.

TABLE III Timeline of the main phases of a hackathon event and orchestration mechanisms

Pre-event	Start of the event	Solution development	Pitching	Evaluation	Post-event
Relational brokering: Providing access to networks, bringing diverse networks together					
Collaboration brokering and facilitation					
Aligning interests					
Team selection and matchmaking					
Configuring interaction between different participation formats					

Contextual configuring: Creating a favorable environment for learning, experimenting, and experiences					
	Ad hoc adaptation of hackathon format				
Designing and adapting format based on continuous feedback					Designing and adapting format based on continuous feedback
Clarity in roles, rules, and criteria					
Legitimacy building: Attracting acceptance, resources, and attention to the issue, technology, or solution					
Orchestrator-focused legitimation			Orchestrator-focused legitimation		
Building a network of affiliated partners and supporters				Building a network of affiliated partners and supporters	
Hackathon challenge framing and scope adjustment					
Momentum building					
	Utilizing space and surroundings to increase prominence				

5. IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

We know a great deal about the overall organization of hackathons (for a review, see Heller et al., 2023). However, we have lacked a more nuanced understanding of what hackathon orchestration constitutes, given the loosely coupled nature and voluntary participation typical of hackathons (Endrissat & Islam, 2022). With the help of comprehensive qualitative data on hackathon organizing – conducted by a professional hackathon orchestrator company – revealed three distinct orchestration practices for hackathons: relational brokering, contextual configuring, and legitimacy building. We have also demonstrated how these mechanisms

benefit solvers and partners in hackathons, and how they become relevant across different phases of hackathon events, including pre-, during, and post-event phases.

5.1 Theoretical implications

First, our study contributes to and extends the literature on hackathons by empirically unbundling the different orchestration mechanisms of hackathon organizers that aim to broker, configure, and legitimize hackathons. We demonstrate how these three distinctly different orchestration mechanisms complement one another to benefit hackathon partners and solvers. As such, we contribute to the literature on hackathon coordination (Heller et al., 2023; Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021; Pihlajamaa & Merisalo, 2021) from an orchestration perspective, where we highlight the social network features of hackathons and demonstrate the mechanisms in which the hackathon organizer, acting as a boundary spanner (Bullinger et al., 2010), can facilitate, configure, and refine relationships and the network contexts in which hackathon partners and solvers interact.

Second, while much hackathon research has discussed hackathons as events coordinated by corporates, individuals, non-profits, or other focal organizations (see, e.g., Bullinger et al., 2010; Cavallo & Burgers, 2024; Heller et al., 2023), our empirical results provide a more nuanced understanding of the role of a separate third-party entity orchestrating hackathons. The literature suggests third-party orchestration is beneficial because it provides neutral, facilitative coordination in a variety of collaborative settings (Pinnington et al., 2021; Ritala et al., 2023). We demonstrate how the third-party role of a professional hackathon orchestrator facilitates a range of orchestration practices that help intermediate connections and ideas, configure collaboration settings, and legitimize the activity as a whole. In this regard, we follow literature suggesting that orchestration encompasses individual skills and organizational capabilities that

are particularly useful in innovative and facilitative settings (Hurmelinna-Laukkanen & Nätti, 2018; Ritala et al., 2009).

Finally, we contribute to the literature that portrays network orchestration as a process of brokering (Ritala et al., 2023). We demonstrate not only how hackathon orchestration resembles the classic notions of network brokering in terms of bridging structural holes (Burt, 2004) but also the important role of modifying the context in which the network of actors interacts, which represents a more recent notion in the brokering process (Halevy et al., 2019). Brokering practices by the orchestrator to foster social interactions mainly occur informally, leading to such brokering practices being referred to as invisible labor for coordination and often being overlooked (Halevy et al., 2019, p. 222). For instance, brokering practices for both bridging ties (i.e., introducing individuals to each other) and altering the context so that individuals can more easily interact may be specifically suited to brokering collaborations with new solvers who are unfamiliar with a setting (Lingo & O'Mahony, 2010). Our study extends these insights by highlighting a third brokering process that we call legitimacy building. This finding resonates with existing ecosystem orchestration literature illustrating the important role of orchestrators in creating and accumulating legitimacy in an ecosystem (Thomas & Ritala, 2022). Our study brings the notion of legitimacy to the hackathon literature where we demonstrate how legitimacy building contributes to better resourcing and status for hackathon events and hackathon partners and solvers in terms of perceptions of status and opportunity, which are important drivers of hackathon participation.

5.2 Practical implications

While hackathons have existed for several decades, the professional organizing and linking of different networks and the art of orchestration at them are still emerging. Universities or firms

have often organized hackathons as internal innovation contests, and hackathon organizing as a third-party activity is still a nascent sector. It is important to remember that the impacts of well-orchestrated hackathons materialize long after the events themselves. The organizers we interviewed observed that it often takes at least 12–18 months for the solutions developed to be implemented in the form of new ventures or product introductions.

The orchestrator plays a central role in bringing together hackathon partners and solvers because orchestration practices significantly influence the quality of a hackathon event, its outcomes, and the engagement and satisfaction of all involved. For instance, defining and communicating the hackathon's purpose, objectives, and challenges is crucial for the experience of individual solvers. At the same time, the orchestrator needs to effectively mobilize the most appropriate resources and manage relationships between solvers and partners on an inter-organizational level. For these reasons, we portray hackathon orchestration as brokerage, which requires the organizer to facilitate and manage social networks in various ways. Identifying three orchestration practices offers a useful starting point for hackathon organizers determining their approach to future events.

Hackathons also provide a unique perspective on the orchestration of social networks in more general terms. The hackathon context highlights the crucial orchestrator's role in defining challenges, mobilizing resources, and managing relationships, resembling the dynamics in many other social networks that are less purposefully organized. Furthermore, the role of technology in mediating these interactions in both online and hybrid hackathons and the affective environment created can provide insights into emotional ties, the dynamics of collaboration, and innovation in general (Endrissat & Islam, 2022).

5.3 Limitations and further research

Case study research has limitations, such as the difficulty in generalizing findings to a broader population due to the uniqueness of each case. All hackathons studied in the current research were organized by a single, highly experienced orchestrator. However, we believe that the rich data obtained enabled us to identify the three key mechanisms of hackathon orchestration, especially when conducted via a third-party actor. Future research might address this study's limitations and boundary conditions, expand on its findings by investigating hackathons using different coordination models or different temporal orientations, and report on the long-term effects and outcomes of hackathons; we discuss these ideas in more detail next.

While our study examined how third parties (in this case, Ultrahack) orchestrate hackathons, there is room for further studies to examine how our orchestration mechanisms play out in other organizational settings. For instance, more conventional firm-organized hackathons might have different dynamics in terms of legitimacy and resourcing, especially if they are organized with (partially) firm-internal crowds. Alternatively, fully online hackathons might involve different dynamics, especially regarding relational brokering mechanisms (see also Kathan et al., 2015, on open virtual contest platforms). Future studies could examine how a different types of digital platforms enable gathering innovative ideas and inputs (for instance, see Cennamo et al., 2022 and Ritala, 2024 on the PatientInnovation platform), and how such platforms could incorporate a variety of hackathon orchestration mechanisms. Furthermore, similarly to the entrepreneurial ecosystems context (Tabas et al., 2023), hackathon orchestrators could adopt broader community roles beyond the immediate brokering activities. This could include building innovation communities that involve repeated hackathon dynamics, as in the *makerspaces* context (Browder et al., 2023). In this regard, expanding our understanding of orchestration

mechanisms to encompass broader community empowerment would be an interesting research option.

Second, future studies could focus on how time and temporality affect hackathon orchestration and outcomes. Hackathons are often time-constrained and utilize time pressure when it comes to the creative endeavors of solvers (Lodato & DiSalvo, 2016; Lifshitz-Assaf et al., 2021). This could lead to focusing (or over-focusing) the legitimation efforts on discursive mechanisms attempting to maximize the resourcing of and participation in a single hackathon event rather than building long-term continuity into hackathon organizing. Furthermore, in our empirical context, the hackathons followed a format with pre- during- and post-event phases. To build further on our findings, other types of hackathon designs could be studied to examine what types of orchestration mechanisms are highlighted when the hackathon design differs from the individual event -style, or if more time is allocated to different phases. For example, it would be interesting to study longer-term, multi-stage hackathons that allocate more time to different hackathon phases, as well as hackathon organizing schemes that involve even longer community building (as discussed previously). Future studies might devise experiments and identify case studies to examine how time and temporality affect hackathons and their orchestration.

Finally, research often neglects the post-hackathon phase (Flores et al., 2018). However, scrutinizing the phase following the end of a hackathon and the resulting ideas, presentations, and prototypes could yield valuable insights into projects with a potential for further development. Follow-up studies examining how hackathon orchestration affects outcomes and whether particular mechanisms are linked to beneficial outcomes following the hackathons would be welcome.

Appendix 1 Interview guides

Hackathon solvers: specific questions

- What was your contribution to the hackathon lineup?
- Before you joined the hackathon, what were your expectations of it and the actors involved in it?
 - expectations of the event?
 - expectations of the organizer?
 - expectations of the sponsors or of the other participants?
 - expectations regarding processes, learnings, or socializing?
- What did you know about the organizer or hackathons in general before the event (and did you search for information? from the media, the Internet, from friends?)
 - How did the organizer (or other actors) communicate about the hackathon?
Which channels did they use?
 - What makes hackathons appear credible and understandable to everyone?
(In the hackathon event and outside of it?) Can you give examples?
 - How can the organizers affect the credibility and understandability of hackathons? Please give examples.
- How do you see acceptance of the hackathon?
 - by people participating in the event.
 - by people not involved in the event.
- What were your impressions of the organizers?
 - Can you give examples?
- How do you see the acceptance of the hackathon organizer's activities?

- In your view, how was the hackathon perceived?
 - Can you give examples?
- Can you summarize your experience of this hackathon?
 - What did you like, and what did you dislike?
 - Regarding fairness in this hackathon, what was fair or unfair about the rules or organizing? Please give examples.
- What has happened since the event? What was the feeling when the Hackathon ended?
 - Did your perceptions change during the hackathon, and why?
- What are your thoughts on the scheduling of hackathons? Should they have a limited timeframe with a clear beginning and an end?
 - What are the main advantages and disadvantages of this limited timeframe?
 - How did others at the hackathon perceive that?
 - How does the organizer deal with the limited timeframe?
- How did you find sharing your ideas with a group of people you did not know before?
 - How did you develop trust in your team over a short space of time? Did you notice or have any reservations?
- Were any of your expectations of the hackathon unmet?
- Does the goal of a hackathon affect your perception of it?
 - What was the overall goal of the hackathon? Did you think or reflect on that goal?
 - How did the goal and topic of the hackathon affect your motivation or actions before and during the hackathon?

- For instance, goals relating to sustainable development or social welfare?
- How would you compare such goals to commercial or technology-driven ones?
- Do you think hackathons lead to innovation?
 - How do they lead to innovation? Can you give some examples?

Hackathon Partners: specific questions

- What was the reason for becoming a client participating in a hackathon?
 - (& specifically, a client of the organizer?)
- How did the organizer convince you as a client or partner to participate in the hackathon?
- What are the benefits of being a client of the organizer?
- How do you see the acceptance of the hackathon?
 - by people participating in the event?
 - by people not involved in the event?
- How did you perceive the organizers?
 - Can you give some examples?
- How do you see the acceptance of the organizer's activities?
- How was the event judged (i.e., the hackathon itself)?
 - Can you give some examples?
- What were your impressions of the participants and the challenges?
- How was your collaboration with the mentors? What were the benefits and/or challenges?
- Did you participate in the matchmaking process?
 - If yes, how do you facilitate that process for hackathon participants?

- What strategies create successful hackathon events?
- How has the offering by the organizer benefited (or disadvantaged) the progress of your internal project?
 - (What do you think are the reasons?)

Hackathon orchestrators: specific questions

- What was your way into the hackathon sphere?
- How would you explain a hackathon to a layperson?
- How are hackathons generally organized? (Is there a structure?)
- What benefits does the organizer offer?
- How do you (the organizers) attract clients?
- How do you (the organizers) attract participants/hackers?
- How do you facilitate interactions between members?
- How is matchmaking done before the hackathon?
- How do you create/support alignment between hackers in a team?
- What do they provide that supports a successful/good hackathon materializing?
- What factors led to the failure of some teams or entire hackathon challenges?
- What makes a team or an entire hackathon successful?
- How can tensions between members of a hackathon team be resolved?
- Why?
- Why do clients, other stakeholders, or solvers participate?
 - What motivates them?
 - What is their real or perceived benefit?
- What is the management style?
 - (What do you think are the reasons? - Can you give examples?)

- What is the role of the different stakeholders?
 - (What do you think are the reasons? - Can you give examples?)
- How are the goals and the design of the hackathon shaped?
 - by whom?
 - by the organizer or clients?
 - through what kind of actions? (Examples?)
- How is the identity of a hackathon event shaped?
- How do you/the organizer try to influence how other external actors
 - perceive and form opinions of the organizer?
 - impressions they gather about the organizer?
 - media, competitors, financial analysts, regulators
- Please tell me about some successful and unsuccessful attempts.
 - Successful attempts – (What do you think are the reasons? - Can you give examples?)
 - Unsuccessful attempts (What are the reasons? - Can you give examples?)
- Potential clients – How does the organizer try to influence how potential clients or external actors perceive and form an opinion of the organizer?
- Potential hackathon participants - how does the organizer try to influence how potential participants, as external actors, perceive and form an opinion of the organizer?
- Society at large - how does the organizer try to influence society at large, or how do external actors perceive and form an opinion of the organizer?
 - (What do you think are the reasons? - Can you give examples?)

- What are the critical moments for the organizer to help actors build an understanding of what the organizer does?
 - Clients, partners, participants, external actors (media, competition, regulators...)
- What are the critical moments for the organizer where actors build acceptance of what UH does?
- What are the critical moments for the organizer where actors build a positive evaluation and acceptance of what the organizer does?

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